

Job Satisfaction and Organizational Commitment (Study of Commercial Banks of Sukkur Region, Sindh, Pakistan)

Author's Details:

⁽¹⁾Sarmad Rahat-Lecturer, Department of Economics, Shah Abdul Latif University, Khairpur, Sindh, Pakistan-⁽²⁾Urooj Talpur-Assistant Professor, Department of Economics, University of Sindh, Jamshoro, Pakistan-⁽³⁾Dr. Khalid Noor Panhwar-Assistant Professor, Department of Public Administration, University of Sindh, Jamshoro, Pakistan-⁽⁴⁾ Mohammad Ali Pasha Panhwar-Lecturer, Department of Economics, University of Sindh, Jamshoro, Pakistan

Abstract

As the study of job satisfaction and organizational commitment is too much debatable and research oriented, in this regard we choose it to work out with the commercial banking sector (public and private) of Sukkur region, by collecting data through the questionnaire, personally providing and receiving the responses from different level of personnel in officer grade and get it analyzed through SPSS. 16. Through reliability analysis, factor analysis, linear regression, and finally the Pearson 1-tailed correlation, and concluded that organizational commitment and job satisfaction is highly correlated with each other and organizational commitment is positively related to job satisfaction (significant).

Key Words: Job Satisfaction, Organizational Commitment, Commercial Banks

Introduction

Basically the psychological attachment of the individuals with their organization is known as organizational commitment, many studies was and still on the way to improve the behavior of workers towards their organization. Vast literature is available in the area of organizational commitment and job satisfaction which predicts some work related variables. Job satisfaction is simply the cognitions about the job. Organizational commitment and job satisfaction are relatively most attentive from researcher's point of view around the world, because committed and satisfied employees are the high performers and contributing a lot to their organization. The successfulness of any organization is not only depending on how the organization makes human competencies but also working on the stimulation of commitment towards organization (Beukhof, De Jong, & Nijhof, 1998; Thornhill, Lewis, & K. Saunders, 1996).

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this research was to explore the relationship between job satisfaction and organizational commitment among the employees of commercial banks working in sukkur region, sindh, Pakistan.

Literature Review

Many researchers reported mixed findings of relationship between organizational commitment and job satisfaction (Curry, Wakefield, Price, & Mueller, 1986) found that there is no significant relationship between organizational commitment and job satisfaction.

Study of (Syed, 2010) concluded that age and job tenure significantly predicting organizational commitment, and these results are consistent with findings of other researchers; that the older workers are more committed to their organizations than the newer ones (Dodd-McCue & Wright, 1996).

In now days managers of different organizations have much importance on the matter of job satisfaction of their employees. This is only because when employees are satisfied are likely to be more committed to their organization. Workers in return, are mostly pride to be the member of that organization, believing on the values and goals of organization, and work with higher performance and productivity (Steinhaus & Perry, 1996).

Nasurdin & Ramayah (2003), have pointed out many studies on organizational commitment and its predictors, by using Malaysia, and concluded that that there were small number of studies which are purely focusing the relationship between job satisfaction and organizational commitment.

Study of Samad & Sarminah (2011), examined the relationship between organizational commitment and job performance, and the results revealed that there is a positive relationship between organizational commitment and job performance, and hierarchical analysis identified that job satisfaction played moderating role in between the organizational commitment and job performance.

The study of Rohmi, Mishan, Nair, & Haryanni (2012), examined the level of job satisfaction, organizational commitment and the turnover intention among employees in retail setting, and recommended that satisfaction with salary, promotion, supervisor and work it self has got significant influence on turnover intentions.

Despite of several studies on affective commitment only few studies of organizational commitment has been conducted by non US and non UK countries like Canada, Belgium, Russia, South Korea, Singapore, Japan, and China (Cheng & Stockdale, 2003; Lee, Allen, Meyer, & Rhee, 2001; Vandenberghe, 1996). However the most of these researches are limited to the examination of construct validity of (Meyer & Allen, 1991).

Research Model

Diagnostic Test

$$JS = \alpha + OC (\beta) + \mu$$

Data Collection

A questionnaire was designed which comprises of two factors “job satisfaction” and “organizational commitment” with the total set of 47 questions and five point scale was used to measure the responses from different respondents of banks working in sukkur region, total 205 responses were received from almost 300.

Analysis

All the responses were entered in SPSS. 16 and at first instance reliability was checked through cronbach’s alpha which was ($\alpha = 0.863$). and then factor analysis was used to reduce the full data in to two factors for checking the interrelationship of the variables. And finally the linear regression was applied to check the nature of relationship between the variables and overall model fit.

Results and Discussion

Model Summary

Model	R	R-Square	Adjusted R-Square	Std. Error of the Estimates
1	.781	.610	.602	.63062421

Results in the table of model summary states that overall model accordingly mentioned in the diagnostic test is fit by looking at the value of **Adjusted R-Square** that is .602 which means the independent variable of organizational commitment is rightly predicting the dependent variable of job satisfaction, which is much satisfactory and significant .000 level in the banking sector and Pakistani perspective, while comparing these

results with other studies organizational commitment got little bit and somewhere no effect or insignificant type of relation in different studies of the countries.

ANOVA

	Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Significance
1	Regression	32.320	1	32.320	81.271	.000
	Residual	20.680	52	.398		
	Total	53.000	53			

Regression model 1 states about the error term of the regression equation from the residual which is 20.680 from total of 53.000, remaining was covered by the regression model and that model is significant at .000 level.

Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficient	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 Constant	7.444E-17	.086		.000	1.000
Organizational Commitment	.781	.087	.781	9.015	.000

And looking at the standardized Beta of organizational commitment i.e. 0.781 which is also significant at .000, results clearly states the positive relationship of organizational commitment with the job satisfaction of employees working in the commercial banks (public and private) of Sukkur region.

Correlation

		Job Satisfaction	Organizational Commitment
Job Satisfaction	Pearson Correlation	1	.781*
	Sig. (1-tailed)		.000
Organizational Commitment	Pearson Correlation	.781*	1
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.000	

* Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (1-tailed)

While looking at the pearson 1-tailed correlation Organizational commitment is highly correlated with job satisfaction and also the job satisfaction is, both are significant 0.01 level.

Limitations of the Study

The study of job satisfaction and organizational commitment was carried out in the commercial bank (public and private) of Sukkur region only

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